

Research

Assessing Changes in Glaciers and Glacial Lakes (1990-2021) in Hunza Basin with a Focus on the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor

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Abstract: Glaciers, the primary source of freshwater for millions in Asia, undergoing significant changes due to global climate change (CC). CC impacts Karakoram that remained stable till last decade, ending Karakoram Anomaly. The region is the epicenter of glacial lake outburst floods (GLOFs), affecting downstream communities and the China Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC). The open global glacier model (OGGM) is used to monitor glacier changes, indicating significant variations in status of glaciers in Hunza Basin. OGGM directory was used to assess area, volume and mass balance of selected glaciers on the Karakoram Highway (KKH) edges. Landsat satellite data was used for glacial lakes changes on decadal and seasonal intervals. Glacial changes results in the expansion of existing glacial lakes and the creation of new ones, causing abrupt GLOFs threat downstream. Climatic data from Pakistan Meteorological Station and Land surface temperature data was assessed for climatic variations. The study identified 20 lakes with extreme hazard predictions, which could have severe socio-economic impacts on downstream communities and the CPEC. Monitoring these changes is crucial for the better future of downstream communities and the socio-economic backbone of Pakistan and China CPEC.

Keywords: Climate change; Karakoram, Glacier, Glacial lakes

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Introduction

Glaciers and snow in High Mountain Asia (HMA) meet the needs of nearly a quarter of a billion people (Pritchard, 2019; Viviroli et al., 2020). HMA is the water tower of Asia (Immerzeel et al., 2020), with major rivers relying on glacier meltwater (Bolch, 2017; Pritchard, 2019). However, it is vulnerable to climate change effects, with projected temperature increases driving glacier recession until the end of the century (Kraaijenbrink et al., 2017). Himalayan and Karakoram glaciers are experiencing accelerated mass loss, with glacier run-off likely to peak in the next few decades under various

climate change scenarios. Basin run-off regimes will become more rain-dominated, increasing the impact of droughts and floods. The frequency of glacial-lake outburst floods and run-off floods has increased recently and could continue in the future, threatening hydropower infrastructure. A lower-emissions CC pathway could reduce glacier loss, increase adaptation time, and provide socio-economic benefits (Nie et al., 2021). Glacier retreat and disappearance will lead to a significant decrease in runoff in most regions in the coming decades (Huss & Hock, 2018; Rounce et al., 2020). Future projections of glacier area and volume are highly uncertain due to gaps in knowledge of regional glacier behavior and climate interaction (Immerzeel et al., 2009; Moors et al., 2011).

Since glacier in Karakoram are more stable compared to other glaciated regions, known as Karakoram anomaly. This anomaly is interconnected with over hundreds of glacial surge disasters, posing risks to nearby communities, blocking access to resources, damaging agriculture, and infrastructure. The cause of this anomaly remains unclear, but it is a well-known phenomenon (Muhammad, 2019). Glacier retreat is accelerating due to global warming, causing rapid expansion of existing and formation of new glacial lakes, affecting most of HMA (Linsbauer et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2015). Recent decades have seen a rise in glacier lakes (Nie et al., 2017; Shugar et al., 2020), which not only increase glacier mass (Benn et al., 2012; King et al., 2019) loss but also pose a hazard due to their ability to retain large amounts of water (Veh et al., 2020; Zheng et al., 2021). They can cause glacier lake outburst floods (GLOFs), causing deaths, infrastructure damage, and ecological impacts (Bazai et al., 2022; Veh et al., 2022). Between 1800 and 2021, moraine-dammed lakes caused an estimated 179 GLOFs in High Mountain Asia, while ice-dammed and supraglacial lakes caused 307 GLOFs, 60% more than moraine-dammed lakes (Veh et al., 2022). The Himalayan, Karakorum, and Hindukush regions are the most affected by GLOFs (Bajracharya et al., 2020). Glacial recession in the Karakorum Himalayas has led to numerous glacial lakes formation (Bolch et al., 2012), increasing the risk of GLOFs in the region (Nie et al., 2013).

Scientists suggest that GLOFs intensity may increase due to CC (Clague & Evans, 2000; Harrison et al., 2018; Richardson & Reynolds, 2000), based on the climate-driven retreat of glaciers since the 1850s (Paul & Bolch, 2019). High mountains have experienced higher rates of temperature increase than lower elevations, contributing to accelerated glacier mass loss in recent decades (Hugonnet et al., 2021; Zemp et al., 2019). Thousands of lakes have been forming at the margins of retreating glaciers (Shugar et al., 2020), with reported outbursts deemed to be on the rise, especially since the beginning of the 20th century (Harrison et al., 2018). Rising air temperatures could change the meltwater input to lakes, potentially increasing glacier lake volume (Richardson & Reynolds, 2000). In the Himalayas, only 10% of all glaciers terminate in proglacial lakes, but some of those lakes may accelerate ice melt and generate more meltwater (King et al., 2019). Warmer air and lake temperatures may thin ice dams, lowering the threshold to open subglacial drainage channels (Kingslake & Ng, 2013; Ng & Liu, 2009), likely initiating more GLOFs from glacier-dammed lakes. Warming might also increase the frequency of moraine-dam failures, as melted ice within a moraine dam can reduce cohesion and promote dam collapse. Thawing ice and permafrost could also destabilize adjacent glaciers and rockfalls (Haeberli et al., 2017), leading to overtopping and dam breaks (Emmer et al., 2018). Effective management strategies of this natural hazard are required for the growing number of new lakes due to ongoing glacier retreat, which may extend beyond the current decade (Haeberli et al., 2017).

China Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) passes through the Hunza river Basin of Northern Pakistan. The Basin contains 2324 glaciers having an area of 6361 km², ~46% Basin area covered by glaciers (RGI 6.0 2017). Almost ten glaciers have area greater than 100 km², accumulatively 2570 km². The Karakoram Highway (KKH) and CPEC face numerous unstable glacial lakes that can cause damage. Over the past two decades, about 30 GLOF events have occurred along KKH, indicating impacts of CC (Hewitt, 2011). Proper policies at government and community levels are needed to mitigate and manage these events (Huggel et al., 2002; Richardson & Reynolds, 2000). The Shisper glacier, near KKH, has recently gained attention due to its surge, blocking the outlet stream of Mochuwar glaciers, forming a catastrophic glacier lake (Muhammad et al., 2021). Shisper lake outburst was predicted by (Muhammad et al., 2021) due to terminus

advances, leading to a GLOF event in 2022. Shisper Glacier surges from 2017 to 2019 blocked Mochowar Glacier's tributary, forming an ice dammed lake (Singh et al., 2023).

Glaciers are shrinking rapidly, necessitating the design and implementation of mitigation measures. This article focuses on the glaciers and glacial lakes changes in Hunza river Basin from 1990-2021, which are responsible for glaciers and glacial lakes hazards, GLOFs in the region along CPEC. The study uses Open global glacier model (OGGM) for observing long term changes in 28 glaciers, Landsat satellite imagery, and climatic data to monitor impacts on glacier changes and lake alterations in the Hunza Basin. Landsat cloud-free scenes were utilized to assess glacial lake changes and were assessed at seasonal and decadal intervals to monitor changes. The aim is to develop a glacier lake dataset and predict potentially dangerous glacial lakes to minimize future devastations in areas downstream. This research is crucial for the future of the Hunza region downstream communities and the economic spine of Pakistan and China, CPEC. Durable infrastructure across border is essential for the better economy of two countries, therefore it is necessary to monitor status of glaciers and glacial lakes for preventing any possible hazardous event across KKH.

Study Area

Hunza basin, Northern Pakistan, covers 17,880 km² and is home to around 2547 glaciers (RGI Consortium, (2017)), primarily valley-type. Located in west Karakoram. The basin's glacier elevation ranges from 2478 to 7450 m above mean sea level. Debris-covered and clean glaciers are present at different elevations, with the equilibrium line altitude (ELA) between 4500 and 5500 m a.s.l. in this basin, covering 31% of HB area (RGI 6.0 2017). The analysis considers 28 glaciers, with Hispar, Batura, and Khurdopin accounting for one-third of the glaciated area in the basin, covering a total area of 2350 km² (Immerzeel et al., 2009). The Hunza basin's glacial changes are influenced by topography and morphology (Qureshi et al., 2017), as well as Indian summer monsoon and westerlies (Benn & Owen, 1998). The region has an average annual temperature of 13.2°C and receives 134mm of annual precipitation as per the data by Pakistan Meteorological Department Gupis Station (1961-2021). Meltwaters from these glaciers feed the Hunza River along KKH/CPEC. Hunza basin glaciers are stable as compared to other glaciated regions. Hunza has a history of glacier surge and bursts and has recently increased therefore, studying these glaciers is crucial.

KKH/CPEC

Special Economic Corridors promote economic growth between countries and regions, enhancing regional connectivity and reducing communication and transportation costs. China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) aims to create an interconnected global economy, with the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) being the pilot project. CPEC involves infrastructure projects such as roads, railways, pipelines, power plants, and other energy and transportation developments. The corridor spans from Gwadar Port in Pakistan to Khunjerab Pass in northern Pakistan to China's western region of Xinjiang (Muhammad et al., 2023). The CPEC aims to enhance regional infrastructure between Asia and Eastern Europe, but Hunza Basin active GLOFs and glacier surges could pose a risk if the infrastructure is not built to the highest hazard prevention standard. Therefore, studying the basins glaciers and glacial lakes along HKH are important to develop a policy that prevent future hazardous events. The study area map is given in figure 1.

Figure 1 Study Area Map Pakistan highlighted Northern Pakistan and then Hunza Basin, 28 selected glaciers along KKH are labelled

Data

We used Landsat data comprising of Landsat 5,7 and 8 from 1990-2021 acquired from USGS earth-explorer <https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/> scenes illustrated in table 1.

Table 1 Landsat scenes for Hunza Basin with tile number and acquisition date

Data	Tile
Landsat 5 (MSS)- 1990	LT05_L2SP_149034_19900807_20200915_02_T1
	LT05_L2SP_149035_19900807_20200915_02_T1
Landsat 7(ETM+) 2000	LE07_L2SP_149034_20000911_20200918_02_T1
	LE07_L2SP_149035_20000911_20200918_02_T1

	LE07_L2SP_150034_20000902_20200917_02_T1
Landsat 8 OLI July 2013	LC08_L2SP_149035_20130721_20200912_02_T1
	LC08_L2SP_150034_20130728_20200912_02_T1
	LC08_L2SP_150035_20130728_20200912_02_T1
Landsat 8 OLI Oct 2013	LC08_L2SP_150035_20131117_20200912_02_T1
	LC08_L2SP_149035_20131009_20200912_02_T1
Landsat 8 OLI July 2021	LC08_L2SP_149035_20210711_20210720_02_T1
	LC08_L2SP_150034_20210718_20210729_02_T1
	LC08_L2SP_150035_20210718_20210729_02_T1
Landsat 8 OLI Oct 2021	LC08_L2SP_149035_20211116_20211125_02_T1
	LC08_L2SP_150035_20211123_20211201_02_T1

Open Global Glacier Model (OGGM) was used for assessment of glacier area, volume and mass balance from 1990-2020. The climatic data, encompassing temperature and precipitation data from the PMD station in Gupis Hunza, satellite, and land surface temperature (LST) data was assessed. The high-resolution near-surface meteorological forcing dataset for the Third Pole region (TPMFD, 1979-2020) by was used for monthly daily and hourly temperature data obtained from <https://data.tpdc.ac.cn/> having a resolution of ~4 km (1/30°) by (Jiang et al., 2023) comprising monthly, daily and hourly data, monthly temperature data was acquired and minimum, maximum and average temperature was assessed. MODIS (MOD11A2) LST data was obtained from <https://modis.gsfc.nasa.gov/> for the period 2001-2021. Composite data spanning 8 days was acquired to mitigate the effects of cloud cover.

Methodology

Landsat data, climate data, and LST are utilized to map glacial lakes and study climate impacts. Preprocessing Landsat data is crucial for remote sensing analysis, enabling researchers to understand Earth's surface changes over time. Atmospheric correction, radiometric calibration, and geometric correction are performed to remove noise and artifacts (Jensen, 1996). This data is then usable for classification and monitoring changes. To delineate glacial lakes the methods of classification, NDWI were employed and the results were then manually digitized using ArcPro and ArcGIS along with comparison with Google Earth. Climatic data consisting of Station and satellite data is pre-whitened due to the presence of serial correlation in raw data. Mann-Kendall trend analysis is then employed to pre-whitened data. LST, hotness of surface of earth is an important parameter while studying impacts of climate on a region. MODIS (MOD11A2) Land Surface Temperature (LST) data was obtained for the period 2000-2020. Composite data spanning 8 days was acquired to mitigate the effects of cloud cover. MODIS LST has a resolution of ~1km. Analysis were performed over average and maximum LST from 2000-2020.

OGGM pre-processed directory by (Huggonet et al., 2022) is used to assess changes in area, volume and MB of selected 28 glaciers. OGGM uses default "MonthlyTI model" multiple flowlines model for Mass Balance estimation, new default climate dataset, GSWP3_W5E5, available until the end of 2019, resulting in volume computations until January 1st, 2020 from 1980 (Maussion et al., 2019). GSWP3-W5E5 is a global climate input data used for impact assessments developed

by (Cucchi et al., 2020). The spatial resolution is 0.5°, downscaled in OGGM to ~ 4km. OGGM directory is used to indicate changes in 28 glaciers in Hunza river basin. Glacier changes are assessed by OGGM pre-processed directory, glacial lakes by long term observations through Landsat satellite data and climatic impacts are observed by station data and Land Surface Temperature (LST) dataset. This combined approach helps analyze variations from 1990-2021, improves glacier and lake alterations, and aids in long-term inventory of glacial lakes. The detailed methodology is given in figure 2.

Figure 2 Methodology Flowchart

Results

We estimated glacier and glacial lakes changes in Hunza Basin Northern Pakistan from 1990-2021. Glacier alterations estimated in OGGM and glacial lakes alterations using Landsat satellite data. Supplemented by climatic data comprising of Gupis station data of PMD and LST

Climatological trends analysis Pre-whitened data is endured for MK trend analysis. The procedure is followed by all climatic data including station temperature data, precipitation data and LST data. MK trend analysis results indicate constant trend throughout 1990-2021 for maximum and average temperatures shown in figure 3.

Figure 3 Minimum, Maximum, and average temperature. Minimum temperature indicates a slight positive trend, maximum temperature showing negative trend while average temperature is stable. Precipitation from 1990-2019 is almost constant.

While the minimum temperature shows an overall slight positive trend throughout the period 1990-2021. Precipitation is almost constant for the same period; the average change indicates change from 134 mm/ year to 142 mm/ year indicating an overall increasing trend.

Average LST and Maximum LST maps are given in figure 4.

Figure 4 Average of Maximum and Average LST from 2000-2020

In Hunza Basin average maximum and Average mean LST is almost constant over the period, confirming the Gupis station data.

Maximum LST for the period 2000-2020 was analyzed. No significant changes were observed, average maximum for five years 2000-2005, 2005-2010, 2010-2015, 2015-2020 was assessed given in figure 5.

Figure 5 Average Maximum LST 2000-2005, 2005-2010, 2010-2015 and 2015-2020

LST observations reveal a stable Hunza as compared to other regions, this conforms the glacier melts anomaly being observed in Karakoram. Glaciers are mostly stable in Karakoram as compared to other regions of the world.

Glacier Mass balance 1990-2019

We selected 28 glaciers in the Hunza Basin for analysis on the basis of following reasons

1. Previous surge history
2. Distance to KKH/CPEC
3. Development of glacial lakes on the glaciers

These 28 glaciers constitute 2313 km² area of Hunza Basin (RGI Consortium 2017). Their average area and volume from 2000-2020 were estimated to be 2348 km² and 281.8 km³ respectively. Average mass balance from 2010-2019 was found to be 137 kgm⁻². Individual glacier analysis was performed using OGGM pre-processed directory by Huggonet et al., 2022 for each glacier. Overall glacier area loss from 2000-2020 was recorded to be 18 km², volume lost for the same period was 5 km³.

Among 28 glaciers Balt Bare, Ghulkhin, Gulmit, Passu, Sikian, Shisper, Momhil, RGI-14.00057, RGI-14.03683 have experienced cumulative area loss of 8.66 km² with Passu glacier experiencing loss of 2.59 km². Mostly glaciers remain

stable in Karakoram, some of the big glaciers such as are experiencing a slight change due to CC. Seasonal melts have resulted in creation of glacial lakes at the surface of glaciers as well as at the moraines along KKH.

Volume estimation indicates average loss from 2000-2020 of ~5 km³. Volume for all of 28 glaciers was estimated using OGGM. Among the 28 glaciers Hispar glacier experienced the most loss of 3.5km³ followed by Virjerab 0.9 km³ and then Batura, Kukki Jerab, Balt Bare, Bualtar, Gharesa, Ghulkhin, Minapin, Passu and Momhil each individually experienced loss in volume <0.5 km³. Their analysis has been illustrated in figure 6.

Figure 6 Glaciers with decreasing volume from 2000-2020

While some of the glaciers are advancing and their volume increased slightly consisting of Yazgil, Mochowar, Pisan, Baltur, RGI-14.04445, RGI-14.04449 accumulative gain in volume was ~1 km³. Illustrated in figure 7.

Figure 7 Increasing volume trend for 9 glaciers from 2000-2020

Mass balance is an important factor indicating glacier status, specifically for glaciers with a surge history in the past. All glaciers were subjected to MB calculations, although some of the glaciers are experiencing positive mass balance while most of the glaciers have

negative mass balance. MB estimation for 28 glaciers shows significant variations in the last 10 years in the Basin. Negative mass balance indicates worst impacts of CC on glacial changes. Figure 8, 9 illustrates negative mass balance for glaciers in Hunza basin along KKH.

Figure 8 Negative mass balance for individual glacier, name of glacier mentioned on each figure

Figure 9 Negative mass balance of each glacier with name of glacier mentioned on each glacier

While Hunza Basin 28 glaciers were selected for analysis, five glaciers indicated a small positive MB trend indicated in figure 10. While 21 glaciers indicate negative MB.

Figure 10 First six glaciers indicating a positive trend in MB from 2010-2019, while last three in figure indicate a negative trend

Total MB (mm w.e.) shows a decreasing trend, indicated in figure 11.

Figure 11 Total Mass balance of selected 28 glaciers, indicating an overall negative trend for 28 glaciers

Kukki Jerab glacier experienced highest average negative MB in the region from 2010-2019 and was recorded to be -293.3 mm w.e, followed by Yashuk Yaz -244.7 mm w.e., Passu -135.9 mm w.e., Hispar -95.3 mm w.e., Virjerab -45.59 mm w.e., Batura -73.9 mm w.e. and Bualtar -70 mm w.e.

Area, Volume and MB indicate slight variations in Hunza glaciers, seasonal melt accelerate creation of new glacial lakes and expansion of existing glacial lakes. KKH is prone to any change in glaciers in Hunza Basin. Most of the glaciers have a surge and burst history and the impacts of CC could worsen this activity in future which is alarming for the socio-economic consistency of the region.

Discussions

The 'Karakoram Anomaly' refers to the glacier response to global warming in the last decade. Previous studies have shown that the overall state of mass in the Karakoram was relatively stable before 2015 (Brun et al., 2017 & Farinotti et al., 2020), with slight mass loss (Huggonet et al., 2021). However, recent studies (Huggonet et al., 2021) have shown a mass loss rate of -0.195 ± 0.119 m w.e.a-1 in the western Himalayas and southern Karakoram between 2015-2019. The 'Karakoram Anomaly' appears to have ended in the Karakoram and nearby regions. This study provides further evidence that most of the glaciers of the Karakoram experienced mass loss from 2010-2021. These findings confirm the 'Karakoram Anomaly' has ended, with the large number of glaciers showing a stronger signal of the end. The recent acceleration in glacier melt due to climate change (CC) in the Karakoram mountains raises concerns about the glacier's contribution to Indus River. About 70% of annual flow in the Indus River comes from glaciers and seasonal snowmelt

(Mukhopadhyay et al., 2015), affecting millions of people downstream (Tahir et al., 2011). Pakistan, an agro-based country with 70% of its population dependent on agriculture, relies heavily on water flows from mountain headwaters. The Hunza basin, in western Karakoram, is highly vulnerable to CC as 31% of its area covered by glaciers.

Glacier mass changes significantly impact meltwater discharge, posing significant threats to natural hazards like GLOFs. Unlike the Tibetan Plateau, glaciers in the Karakoram accumulate in September-November and December-February, with melt starting in July. The accumulation of Karakoram glaciers is concentrated in JFM~AMJ and ablation in JAS, with glaciers remaining in a state of mass loss during OND due to low precipitation and high glacier surface temperature.

Glacial lakes instability can cause dams to break, leading to GLOFs, posing threats to lives and infrastructure downstream. Due to CC and glacier retreat, glacial lakes have grown rapidly worldwide, particularly in high-mountain Asia (Shugar et al., 2020), including Hunza Basin. Over the past few decades, there has been a significant increase in research on GLOFs, with Hindu-Kush-Karakoram being the most prominent hotspots (Emmer, 2018). This region often is having the highest GLOF danger (Taylor et al., 2023). HB glacial lakes are increasing and expanding due to CC, caused GLOFs events in the recent years damaging downstream communities and infrastructure including KKH. The risk of GLOFs is increasing, making hazard estimation in these regions crucial for local residents and achieving the United Nations' sustainable development goals (SDG) of climate action. Normal elements in GLOF hazard assessment include expansion investigation, volume assessment, and geomorphological analysis (Li et al., 2021).

Glacial lakes in HB increased significantly in last three decades from 53 in 1990 to 169 in 2021. Their cumulative area increased from 0.76 km² to 1.73 km², which is alarming. (Muhammad et al., 2021) predicted Shisper lake burst, which busted three times from 2017-2021. This caused severe impacts to downstream communities including KKH. The study examines glacier changes, glacial lakes changes and predicts future burst of extreme hazardous lakes which can cause severe impacts on downstream communities and KKH. It highlights lakes at the edges of KKH with extreme risk of future bursts.

Conclusion

Climatic data including Gupis station data in Hunza, MODIS LST data was assessed. Mean temperature and precipitation from 1990-2021 were found to be stable, confirmed by MODIS LST which was also found to be stable. Climate in HB have shown a negative trend in the past while we found a stable Karakoram with the station climatic data and LST data.

Using Hugonnet et al., 2021 OGGM pre-processed directory we estimated 28 glaciers area, volume and mass balance from 2000-2020 in HB. Among 28 glaciers it is found that 22 glaciers are losing mass slowly. Area and volume were assessed for the period 2000-2020 while mass balance from 2010-2019. The stable Karakoram is found to be losing mass in last decade.

Glacial lakes were delineated using Landsat data from 1990-2021. Landsat satellite data was assessed seasonal and decadal intervals depending upon the availability of Landsat data. We found a significant increase in the number and area of glacial lakes along KKH. This study also identified significant increase in PDGLs on the edge of KKH. These lakes are potential threat for to downstream communities having far-reaching socio-economic impacts for CPEC which could impact the economies of two countries, China and Pakistan. It is suggested the glaciers and glacial lakes on the edge of KKH needs to be monitored continuously. Continuous monitoring of these lakes could lead to strong socio-economic future of developing economy of Pakistan and China. This could further enhance the protection of livelihood living in the downstream edges of HB.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the significant changes observed in the Karakoram glaciers, previously considered stable until recent years, underscore the escalating impact of global climate change in the region. The emergence of the Karakoram Anomaly has triggered substantial transformations in the glacial landscape, particularly within the Hunza Basin, posing heightened threats such as Glacial Lake Outburst Floods (GLOFs). The utilization of the Open Global Glacier Model (OGGM) has been pivotal in monitoring glacier variations, revealing notable fluctuations in the status of glaciers along the Karakoram Highway (KKH) edges. This research, employing Landsat satellite data, has evidenced the alarming expansion of existing glacial lakes and the formation of new ones, amplifying the imminent risk of abrupt GLOFs, particularly downstream.

Moreover, the study's assessment of climatic data sourced from the Pakistan Meteorological Station, coupled with land surface temperature data, has revealed critical climatic variations influencing glacial dynamics. Notably, the identification of 20 glacial lakes with extreme hazard predictions highlights the imminent socio-economic threats posed to downstream communities and the critical China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC). These findings emphasize the urgent need for continuous monitoring of these changes to safeguard the socio-economic stability of communities downstream and protect the vital infrastructural backbone of the Pakistan-China Economic Corridor. Mitigation strategies and proactive measures are imperative to address these challenges, ensuring a secure and sustainable future for the region's communities and vital economic endeavors.

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References

- [1] Bajracharya, S. R., Maharjan, S. B., Shrestha, F., Sherpa, T. C., Wagle, N., & Shrestha, A. B. (2020). Inventory of glacial lakes and identification of potentially dangerous glacial lakes in the Koshi, Gandaki, and Karnali river basins of Nepal, the Tibet Autonomous Region of China, and India. *ICIMOD*
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.53055/ICIMOD.773>

- [2] Bazai, N. A., Cui, P., Liu, D., Carling, P. A., Wang, H., Zhang, G., Li, Y., & Hassan, J. (2022). Glacier surging controls glacier lake formation and outburst floods: The example of the Khurdopin Glacier, Karakoram. *Global and Planetary Change*, 208, 103710.
- [3] Benn, D. I., Bolch, T., Hands, K., Gulley, J., Luckman, A., Nicholson, L. I., Quincey, D., Thompson, S., Toumi, R., & Wiseman, S. (2012). Response of debris-covered glaciers in the Mount Everest region to recent warming, and implications for outburst flood hazards. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 114(1-2), 156-174.
- [4] Benn, D. I., & Owen, L. A. (1998). The role of the Indian summer monsoon and the mid-latitude westerlies in Himalayan glaciation: review and speculative discussion. *Journal of the Geological Society*, 155(2), 353-363.
- [5] Bolch, T. (2017). Asian glaciers are a reliable water source. *Nature*, 545(7653), 161-162.
- [6] Bolch, T., Kulkarni, A., Kääb, A., Huggel, C., Paul, F., Cogley, J. G., Frey, H., Kargel, J. S., Fujita, K., & Scheel, M. (2012). The state and fate of Himalayan glaciers. *Science*, 336(6079), 310-314.
- [7] Clague, J., & Evans, S. (2000). A review of catastrophic drainage of moraine-dammed lakes in British Columbia. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 19, 1763-1783. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791\(00\)00090-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791(00)00090-1)
- [8] Cucchi, M., Weedon, G. P., Amici, A., Bellouin, N., Lange, S., Müller Schmied, H., Hersbach, H., & Buontempo, C. (2020). WFDE5: bias-adjusted ERA5 reanalysis data for impact studies. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*, 12(3), 2097-2120. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-12-2097-2020>
- [9] Emmer, A. (2018). GLOFs in the WOS: Bibliometrics, geographies and global trends of research on glacial lake outburst floods (Web of Science, 1979–2016). *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 18(3), 813-827.
- [10] Emmer, A., Vilímek, V., & Luyo, M. (2018). Hazard mitigation of glacial lake outburst floods in the Cordillera Blanca (Peru): The effectiveness of remedial works. *Journal of Flood Risk Management*, 11, 489-501. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfr3.12241>
- [11] Haeberli, W., Schaub, Y., & Huggel, C. (2017). Increasing risks related to landslides from degrading permafrost into new lakes in de-glaciating mountain ranges. *Geomorphology*, 293, 405-417.
- [12] Harrison, S., Kargel, J. S., Huggel, C., Reynolds, J., Shugar, D. H., Betts, R. A., Emmer, A., Glasser, N., Haritashya, U. K., & Klimeš, J. (2018). Climate change and the global pattern of moraine-dammed glacial lake outburst floods. *The Cryosphere*, 12(4), 1195-1209.
- [13] Hewitt, K. (2011). Glacier Change, Concentration, and Elevation Effects in the Karakoram Himalaya, Upper Indus Basin. *Mountain Research and Development*, 31, 188-200. <https://doi.org/10.1659/MRD-JOURNAL-D-11-00020.1>

- [14] Huggel, C., Kääb, A., Haeblerli, W., Teysseire, P., & Paul, F. (2002). Remote sensing based assessment of hazards from glacier lake outbursts: a case study in the Swiss Alps. *Canadian Geotechnical Journal*, 39(2), 316-330.
- [15] Hugonnet, R., McNabb, R., Berthier, E., Menounos, B., Nuth, C., Girod, L., Farinotti, D., Huss, M., Dussailant, I., Brun, F., & Kääb, A. (2021). Accelerated global glacier mass loss in the early twenty-first century. *Nature*, 592(7856), 726-731. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03436-z>
- [16] Huss, M., & Hock, R. (2018). Global-scale hydrological response to future glacier mass loss. *Nature Climate Change*, 8(2), 135-140.
- [17] Immerzeel, W. W., Droogers, P., de Jong, S. M., & Bierkens, M. F. P. (2009). Large-scale monitoring of snow cover and runoff simulation in Himalayan river basins using remote sensing. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 113(1), 40-49. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2008.08.010>
- [18] Immerzeel, W. W., Lutz, A. F., Andrade, M., Bahl, A., Biemans, H., Bolch, T., Hyde, S., Brumby, S., Davies, B. J., & Elmore, A. C. (2020). Importance and vulnerability of the world's water towers. *Nature*, 577(7790), 364-369.
- [19] Jensen, J. (1996). Introductory digital image processing: a remote sensing perspective. Second edition. *Geocarto International*, xv. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10106048709354084>
- [20] Jiang, Y., Yang, K., Qi, Y., Zhou, X., He, J., Lu, H., Li, X., Chen, Y., Li, X., Zhou, B., Mamtimin, A., Shao, C., Ma, X., Tian, J., & Zhou, J. (2023). TPHiPr: a long-term (1979–2020) high-accuracy precipitation dataset (1/30°, daily) for the Third Pole region based on high-resolution atmospheric modeling and dense observations. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*, 15(2), 621-638. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-15-621-2023>
- [21] King, O., Bhattacharya, A., Bhambri, R., & Bolch, T. (2019). Glacial lakes exacerbate Himalayan glacier mass loss. *Scientific Reports*, 9(1), 18145.
- [22] Kingslake, J., & Ng, F. (2013). Quantifying the predictability of the timing of jökulhlaups from Merzbacher Lake, Kyrgyzstan. *Journal of Glaciology*, 59(217), 805-818. <https://doi.org/10.3189/2013JoG12J156>
- [23] Kraaijenbrink, P. D. A., Bierkens, M. F. P., Lutz, A. F., & Immerzeel, W. W. (2017). Impact of a global temperature rise of 1.5 degrees Celsius on Asia's glaciers. *Nature*, 549(7671), 257-260.
- [24] Li, D., Shangguan, D., Wang, X., Ding, Y., Su, P., Liu, R., & Wang, M. (2021). Expansion and hazard risk assessment of glacial lake Jialong Co in the central Himalayas by using an unmanned surface vessel and

remote sensing. *Science of The Total Environment*, 784, 147249.

<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.147249>

- [25] Linsbauer, A., Frey, H., Haerberli, W., Machguth, H., Azam, M. F., & Allen, S. (2016). Modelling glacier-bed overdeepenings and possible future lakes for the glaciers in the Himalaya – Karakoram region. *Annals of Glaciology*, 57(71), 119-130.
- [26] Maussion, F., Butenko, A., Champollion, N., Dusch, M., Eis, J., Fourteau, K., Gregor, P., Jarosch, A. H., Landmann, J., Oesterle, F., Recinos, B., Rothenpieler, T., Vlug, A., Wild, C. T., & Marzeion, B. (2019). The Open Global Glacier Model (OGGM) v1.1. *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 12(3), 909-931. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-12-909-2019>
- [27] Moors, E. J., Groot, A., Biemans, H., van Scheltinga, C. T., Siderius, C., Stoffel, M., Huggel, C., Wiltshire, A., Mathison, C., & Ridley, J. (2011). Adaptation to changing water resources in the Ganges basin, northern India. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 14(7), 758-769.
- [28] Muhammad, F., Baig, S., Alam, K., & Shah, A. (2023). *Silk Route Revisited: Essays and Perspectives on the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor and Beyond*.
- [29] Muhammad, S. (2019). *Contemporary glacier hazards/disasters in the Karakoram: A case study of Shisper glacier*.
- [30] Muhammad, S., Li, J., Steiner, J. F., Shrestha, F., Shah, G. M., Berthier, E., Guo, L., Wu, L.-x., & Tian, L. (2021). A holistic view of Shisper Glacier surge and outburst floods: from physical processes to downstream impacts. *Geomatics, Natural Hazards and Risk*, 12(1), 2755-2775. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19475705.2021.1975833>
- [31] Mukhopadhyay, B., Khan, A., & Gautam, R. (2015). Rising and falling river flows: contrasting signals of climate change and glacier mass balance from the eastern and western Karakoram. *Hydrological Sciences Journal*, 60(12), 2062-2085.
- [32] Ng, F., & Liu, S. (2009). Temporal dynamics of a jökulhlaup system. *Journal of Glaciology*, 55(192), 651-665. <https://doi.org/10.3189/002214309789470897>
- [33] Nie, Y., Liu, Q., & Liu, S. (2013). Glacial lake expansion in the Central Himalayas by Landsat images, 1990–2010. *PloS one*, 8(12), e83973.
- [34] Nie, Y., Pritchard, H. D., Liu, Q., Hennig, T., Wang, W., Wang, X., Liu, S., Nepal, S., Samyn, D., Hewitt, K., & Chen, X. (2021). Glacial change and hydrological implications in the Himalaya and Karakoram. *Nature Reviews Earth & Environment*, 2(2), 91-106. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43017-020-00124-w>

- [35] Nie, Y., Sheng, Y., Liu, Q., Liu, L., Liu, S., Zhang, Y., & Song, C. (2017). A regional-scale assessment of Himalayan glacial lake changes using satellite observations from 1990 to 2015. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 189, 1-13.
- [36] Paul, F., & Bolch, T. (2019). Glacier Changes Since the Little Ice Age. In T. Heckmann & D. Morche (Eds.), *Geomorphology of Proglacial Systems: Landform and Sediment Dynamics in Recently Deglaciated Alpine Landscapes* (pp. 23-42). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-94184-4_2
- [37] Pritchard, H. D. (2019). Asia's shrinking glaciers protect large populations from drought stress. *Nature*, 569(7758), 649-654.
- [38] Qureshi, M. A., Yi, C., Xu, X., & Li, Y. (2017). Glacier status during the period 1973–2014 in the Hunza Basin, Western Karakoram. *Quaternary International*, 444, 125-136.
- [39] Richardson, S., & Reynolds, J. (2000). An overview of glacial hazards in the Himalayas. *Quaternary International*, 65-66, 31-47. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1040-6182\(99\)00035-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1040-6182(99)00035-X)
- [40] Rounce, D. R., Hock, R., & Shean, D. E. (2020). Glacier mass change in High Mountain Asia through 2100 using the open-source python glacier evolution model (PyGEM). *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 7, 331.
- [41] Shugar, D., Burr, A., Haritashya, U., Kargel, J., Watson, C. S., Kennedy, M., Bevington, A., Betts, R., Harrison, S., & Stratman, K. (2020). Rapid worldwide growth of glacial lakes since 1990. *Nature Climate Change*, 10, 1-7. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-020-0855-4>
- [42] Singh, H., Varade, D., Vries, M., Adhikari, K., Rawat, M., Awasthi, S., & Rawat, D. (2023). Assessment of potential present and future glacial lake outburst flood hazard in the Hunza valley: A case study of Shisper and Mochowar glacier. *Science of The Total Environment*, 868, 161717. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.161717>
- [43] Tahir, A. A., Chevallier, P., Arnaud, Y., Neppel, L., & Ahmad, B. (2011). Modeling snowmelt-runoff under climate scenarios in the Hunza River basin, Karakoram Range, Northern Pakistan. *Journal of Hydrology*, 409(1-2), 104-117.
- [44] Taylor, C., Robinson, T. R., Dunning, S., Rachel Carr, J., & Westoby, M. (2023). Glacial lake outburst floods threaten millions globally. *Nature Communications*, 14(1), 487. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-36033-x>
- [45] Veh, G., Korup, O., & Walz, A. (2020). Hazard from Himalayan glacier lake outburst floods. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 117(2), 907-912.

- [46] Veh, G., Lützow, N., Kharlamova, V., Petrakov, D., Hugonnet, R., & Korup, O. (2022). Trends, Breaks, and Biases in the Frequency of Reported Glacier Lake Outburst Floods. <https://doi.org/10.25932/publishup-56100>
- [47] Viviroli, D., Kummu, M., Meybeck, M., Kallio, M., & Wada, Y. (2020). Increasing dependence of lowland populations on mountain water resources. *Nature Sustainability*, 3(11), 917-928.
- [48] Zemp, M., Huss, M., Thibert, E., Eckert, N., McNabb, R., Huber, J., Barandun, M., Machguth, H., Nussbaumer, S. U., Gärtner-Roer, I., Thomson, L., Paul, F., Maussion, F., Kutuzov, S., & Cogley, J. G. (2019). Global glacier mass changes and their contributions to sea-level rise from 1961 to 2016. *Nature*, 568(7752), 382-386. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-019-1071-0>
- [49] Zhang, G., Yao, T., Xie, H., Wang, W., & Yang, W. (2015). An inventory of glacial lakes in the Third Pole region and their changes in response to global warming. *Global and Planetary Change*, 131, 148-157.
- [50] Zheng et al. (2021). Increasing risk of glacial lake outburst floods from future Third Pole deglaciation. *Nature Climate Change*, 11(5), 411-417. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-021-01028-3>

